

Report on the organisation and storage of in-situ data

Project Identification	
Project Full Title	Water Scenarios for Copernicus Exploitation
Project Acronym	Water-ForCE
Grant Agreement	101004186
Starting date	01.01.2021
Duration	36 months

Document Identification	
Deliverable number	D4.3
Deliverable Title	Report on recommendations for the storage of data
Type of Deliverable	Report
Dissemination Level	Public (PU)
Work Package	WP4
Leading Partner	USTIR/FVB-IGB

History of Changes		
Date	Version	Comments

04.08.2022	V0	First Concept (Evangelos Spyarakos, USTIR; Igor Igashawara, IGB)
02.09.2022	V0.1	Skeleton Draft for feedback from WP4 members
05.12.2022	V0.9	First complete Draft (Harriet Wilson, USTIR; Josh Millard, USTIR)
03.01.2023	V1.1	Full Draft for internal feedback
09.01.2023	V2.0	Uploaded to the PP. Version approved by the EC
30.08.2023	V2.1	Extended version with the new chapter dedicated to Copernicus In Situ Component (3edata, EMU, USTIR)
29.12.2023	V3.0	Final version submitted. Pages 7-33 added to previously approved V2.0

List of Acronyms

AERONET-OC	Aerosol Robotic Network - Ocean Colour
ACIX-Aqua	Atmospheric Correction Intercomparison Exercise
CUAHSI	Consortium of Universities for the Advancement of Hydrologic Science
EC	European Commission
EEA	European Economic Area
EDI	Environmental Data Initiative
EMLS	European Multi-Lake Survey
EMSO	The European Multidisciplinary Seafloor and water column Observatory (EMSO)
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
ICPDR	International Commission for the Protection of the Danube River
GEMS/WATER	Global Environment Monitoring System for Freshwater
GEOSS	Global Earth Observation Systems of Systems

GRDC	Global Runoff Data Centre
ISIMIP	The Inter-Sectoral Impact Model Intercomparison Project
KNB	The Knowledge Network for Biocomplexity
LIMNADES	Lake Bio-optical Measurements and Matchup Data for Remote Sensing data
MONOCLE	Multiscale Observation Networks for Optical monitoring of Coastal waters, Lakes and Estuaries
NETLAKE	Networking Lake Observatories in Europe
OLA	Observatory on LAkes
PANGAEA	Data Publisher for Earth & Environmental Science
SeaBASS	SeaWiFS Bio-optical Archive and Storage System
SeaWiFS	Sea-viewing Wide Field-of-view Sensor
SWatCH	The Surface Water Chemistry database
VESLA	Water Quality section of the Finnish Surface Water Information System
VISS	Vatten Informations System Sverige; Water Information Systems Sweden

WISA

The Water Information System Austria

Table of Contents

1. Introduction	2
1.1 Water-ForCE	2
1.2 Purpose of the document / Context	3
1.3 Scope of the report	3
1.4 Definitions	4
1.4.1 In-situ data	4
1.4.2 Database and data storage	5
2. Part 1: Review of the Copernicus In Situ Component	7
2.1 Overview of the Copernicus In Situ Component	7
2.2 Inventory of water related products in CIS2	8
2.2.1 Water Products	8
2.2.2 In situ requirements for existing products in CIS2 database	9
Requirements	9
Definition Level	9
Relevance Level	10
Criticality	11
Barriers	12
Compliance Level	13
Datasets	14
2.3 The current role of Copernicus In Situ Component related to water	17
2.3.1 Previous analysis of Copernicus In Situ Component	17
2.3.2 Water-ForCE analysis of in situ data landscape: needs, gaps and solutions	19

2.4 Water-ForCE specific recommendations for Copernicus In Situ Component	33
3. Part 2 - Review of external in-situ data repositories	34
3.1 Repository Purpose	39
3.1.1 Project-based repositories	39
3.1.2 Monitoring scheme repositories	39
3.1.3 Open data repositories	40
3.1.4 Open managed data repositories	40
3.1.5 Metadata repositories	41
3.1.6 Project-based databases	41
3.2 Data scope	42
3.3 Intended users	42
3.4 Funding	42
3.5 Data providers	44
3.6 Data provider interface	44
3.7 Repository content	45
3.7.1 Variables	45
3.7.2 Water-bodies considered	46
3.7.3 Spatial scope	46
3.7.4 Temporal scope	46
3.7.5 Database types	47
3.7.6 Versions and updates	47
3.7.7 Unique identifiers	47
3.7.8 Metadata	47
3.7.9 Storage	50

3.8 End-user interface	50
3.8.1 Findability	50
3.8.2 Downloading data & data permission	51
3.8.3 Help support	51
3.8.4 Download and machine-readability	51
3.9 End-users	52
4. Future needs and recommendations	54
4.1 Barriers to the uptake/use of in-situ data repositories by satellite-EO end-users	54
4.2 Challenges faced by in-situ data providers, gatherers, and database managers	57
4.4 Recommendations	58
4.4 Future possibilities for storing in-situ data	61
4.4.1 Metadata repositories for in-situ data	61
4.4.2 Extend an existing database	61
4.4.3 A built-for-purpose repository	62
5. Conclusion	63
References	64
Supplementary Material	66

Executive summary

This report summarises the optimal data information and framework for coupling in-situ data and satellite-EO products. Firstly, the Copernicus In situ Component was reviewed and the needs and gaps identified. Secondly, a review of other existing in-situ databases and interviews with data managers highlighted needs for the future organisation and storage of in-situ data for use with satellite-EO products were identified. Actions that may facilitate the wider use of in-situ data within satellite-EO projects were emphasised.

The review revealed the need for a more extensive in situ component for developing global water products within the Copernicus portfolio. The main recommendation for this is to establish or promote a dedicated programme of supersites. Secondly the review of external in situ databases demonstrates the current landscape of in situ water databases and provides recommendations to improve this. The document is organised as below:

- Review of the Copernicus In situ component metadata base, CIS2.
- Description of existing in-situ databases of water quality, water quantity and water-leaving reflectance data from inland and coastal waters,
- Review of the characteristics of the databases highlighting advantages and challenges for coupling with satellite-EO projects, including the data organisation, data format, metadata description and data quality,
- Summary of the needs and recommendations of in-situ databases for improved use with satellite-EO.

Disclaimer

The Information, documentation and figures available in this deliverable are written by the Water-ForCE Consortium members and do not necessarily reflect the view of the EC.

This document is partly based on the EC's official documents however, no legal responsibility can be taken for the contents in this document. Any doubt regarding

administration and reporting should be solved by consulting the official documents or through the Coordination Team, who will consult for an official EC response, if necessary.

1. Introduction

1.1 Water-ForCE

The Horizon-2020 project Water-ForCE (Water scenarios For Copernicus Exploitation) will develop a Roadmap for Copernicus Inland Water Services.

The Roadmap will contain:

- Analysis of user communities' landscape
- Analysis on how Copernicus water-related services can support policy development and monitoring of their implementation
- Gap analysis of the Copernicus water-related service portfolio
- Identification of future potential higher-level biogeochemical products
- Technical requirements for future Copernicus sensors to improve the water-related service portfolio
- Proposal for organising in-situ measurement networks to validate Copernicus remote sensing and modelling products and to provide complementary data not collected by remote sensing
- Proposal on how to define relationships between Core Services and Downstream services
- Scenarios of the most optimal delivery of water services to different user communities.

The Water-ForCE project is coordinated by the University of Tartu (Estonia) with 20 participating organisations from all over Europe. It

connects experts in water quality and quantity, in policy, research, engineering and service sectors.

This report is part of Work Package 4 (WP4) “Aligning in-situ and satellite Earth observation activities” which is trying to establish clear links between in-situ and satellite observation networks to ensure that they can mutually benefit from data collection and sharing

1.2 Purpose of the document / Context

It is widely recognised that a combined approach of in-situ and satellite data can deliver a powerful combination to observe and verify change at the frequency needed to respond to hydrological events and provide early warning. Furthermore, the in situ component is needed to provide high quality and accurate remote sensing and modelling products.

The recent COINS report entitled “Lake water quality in-situ data requirements and availability” (Carvalho et al., 2021), highlighted the gaps in existing water quality in-situ data repositories for the development of satellite-EO products. They called for greater consideration on the design of in-situ sampling programs and protocols for satellite-EO users (D4.2) and the further investigation into existing repositories (this report). Other deliverables, D2.2 for water quality and D3.2 for water quantity, also call for the lack of specific types of in situ data.

1.3 Scope of the report

Task 4.3 Data integration within and between observation networks aimed to assess the current landscape and provide best practices on methods and frameworks for combining in-situ data with Earth Observation data to improve inland water monitoring. The communities of in-situ data providers (identified in T4.1) and remote sensing experts (identified in T2.1) were consulted on the evaluation of the optimal data information

and framework needed for coupling these two communities. In addition to the user feedback, we also review existing databases and discuss with data managers. Considerations include data format, metadata description, and data quality. To summarise, the objectives of this report were:

- To assess the contribution of the Copernicus In situ component towards water related products.
- To form a list of existing in-situ databases of water quality, water quantity and water-leaving reflectance data from inland and coastal waters that are relevant for satellite-EO data users.
- To review the characteristics of these databases highlighting advantages and challenges for coupling with satellite-EO projects, including the data organisation, data format, metadata description and data quality.
- To identify the barriers of uptake by satellite-EO users, the challenges faced by data managers/curators and provide future recommendations for improved organisation and storage of in situ data.

1.4 Definitions

1.4.1 In-situ data

In this report, **in-situ data** refers to measurements collected directly from the location of interest (e.g. soil moisture collected using a probe in the soil) usually represented as numbers (or text and multimedia). Variables are usually considered as water quality (WP2) and water quantity (WP3).

For water quality, we consider 1) in-situ biogeochemical data, and 2) direct and derived radiometric quantities separately. These two types of water quality in situ data have different applications in EO satellite development and have different recommendations in WP2 (D2.2, D2.3).

Water leaving reflectance was selected as it is key to matching in-situ data to satellite data, and hence was included in addition to the two

broader categories of water quality and quantity. In-situ data can be collected at different frequencies for varied time periods and represent different spatial areas. Data may be collected for different reasons, for example as part of a project sampling campaign or a long-term monitoring program. The data may be compiled in a dataset associated with a unique body of work. Inland and coastal water in situ data may be coupled or matched with satellite-EO products for various applications, including:

- Cal/Val of satellite data.
- To fill temporal and spatial observational gaps within in-situ monitoring schemes (or vice versa to fill gaps in satellite time series due to cloud cover for example).
- To train and test machine learning models.
- To develop satellite algorithms (e.g. to detect cyanobacteria).

1.4.2 Database and data storage

The following terminology is used in this document.

- A **data table** is a tabular representation of data, e.g. a single excel spreadsheet.
- A **dataset** is one or more data tables (e.g. an excel file with 1 or more sheets).
- A **database** is an organised collection of datasets that are interlinked or inter-referenced between them (e.g. a project on GitHub or a data package on Zenodo). This is sometimes described as a data package by certain repositories.
- A **repository**, barring any domain specific usage, is a term to describe a location for storing data (e.g. Github or Zenodo).
- A **metadata repository** is a term for a data aggregator or indexer, which does not store the actual datasets on their servers but they do store the actual metadata on their servers (e.g. GEOSS portal).

The organisation and storage of data is important for the future use and re-use of the data and has a direct impact on the end-users of the data. Repositories are typically built with the intention of being easily accessed, managed, and updated. Key existing sources for both abstract and practical guidelines on the best-practice of data repositories, especially within the scientific research or satellite-EO community, include:

- The FAIR Data Principles; Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (Wilkinson et al., 2016).
- TRUST principles for digital repositories; Transparency, Responsibility, User Focus, Sustainability, Technology (Lin et al., 2020).
- Open Geospatial Consortium Standards and Resources (<https://www.ogc.org/>).
- Re3 Registry of research data repositories (<https://www.re3data.org/>).
- Trust Core Seal for repositories (<https://www.coretrustseal.org>).

2. Part 1: Review of the Copernicus In Situ Component

2.1 Overview of the Copernicus In Situ Component

Copernicus In Situ is based on the critical role of in situ data in the calibration, validation, and complementation of Copernicus operational satellite data and products.

As it is defined in its official description, “the Copernicus In Situ Component maps the landscape of in situ data availability, identifies data access gaps or bottlenecks, supports the provision of cross-cutting data and manages partnerships with data providers to improve access and use conditions”.

Since 2010, the European Environment Agency (EEA) has been entrusted to the Copernicus In Situ Component. This started with the GEMS in situ Coordination project (funded by the EC), aiming to develop a clear understanding of in situ data requirements, to clarify the collaboration framework required to respond to them and to develop case studies of solutions. EEA coordination role is consolidated by its 2014 Delegation Agreement with the European Commission.

While the various Services are responsible for acquiring and managing the in situ data used for production and validation of their own data products, Copernicus In Situ Component acts as a cross-cutting and coordinating body at a program level improving the provision of the in situ data, benefitting several Copernicus services, keeping also an up-to-date overview of in situ data requirements from the whole Copernicus product portfolio.

The fundamental approach to in situ data provision by the Copernicus In Situ Component states that it should be drawn on different data sources, including mainly and preferably Member States data, and to the extent that it is necessary, third-party data sources. The observing networks are owned and operated by institutions and agencies at national level and can be coordinated by frameworks at EU or international level.

Scientific research networks based on national and EU research funds are a critical source of in situ data for the Copernicus programme; while managed as research resources, are crucial to operational Copernicus activities.

In situ data for Copernicus include: ground-based, sea-borne or air-borne monitoring systems, as well as geospatial reference or ancillary data.

2.2 Inventory of water related products in CIS2

The current report comprises the findings of the review of the existing products within the Copernicus in-situ database (CIS2), for both water quantity and quality, and then assessed the in-situ requirements for these existing products and the degree to which they are being met.

2.2.1 Water Products

There are a total of 844 water quantity related products (Water-ForCE deliverable D3.2) of which 698 are direct estimates of water within land and coastal environments.

Table 1. Summary of water quantity related products from Deliverable 3.2. Those that are water-related are in yellow, while those that are often used in water quantity modelling are included in the overall count but not highlighted.

Parameter Group	Climate (C3S)	Atmosphere (CAMS)	Emergency (CEMS)	Land (CLMS)	Marine (CMEMS)	Total
Anthropogenic			1			1
Drought	4		8	7		19
Evapotranspiration	45	2				47
Floods			41			41
Geographic zones				10		10
Ground motion				3		3
Humidity	23	1				24
Hydrology	55		5	2		62
Land cover/Land use	10	10		59		79
Precipitation	68	8	19			95
Snow & Ice	159	6	7	10	41	223
Soil	36		11	6		53
Water storage	107	34				141
Waterbodies	24	2	1	19		46
Total	531	63	93	116	41	844

In contrast, currently there are only 6 products available which are directly relevant for water quality issues (D2.2).

Table 2. Summary of water quality related products.

Parameter Group	Climate (C3S)	Atmosphere (CAMS)	Emergency (CEMS)	Land (CLMS)	Marine (CMEMS)	Total
Chlorophyll-a					1	1
Light backscattering					1	1
Total suspended matter					1	1
Turbidity				1	1	2
Trophic State Index				1		1
Total	0	0	0	2	4	6

2.2.2 In situ requirements for existing products in CIS2 database

Requirements

In the CIS2 database, **160 relevant water products** were identified, excluding open ocean products. It is worth noting that not all Copernicus products were found in the CIS2 database. For example, the Land Service lake water quality products were not found on the CIS2 database. Additionally, 44 of the products found did not have any requirements listed on the CIS2 database. For the remaining 116 existing products, there were **454 requirements** for in situ data (See Table S1 in Supplementary Material for the full list of these *in situ* requirements).

Definition Level

The definition level determines how clear the requirement definition is which is essential for a product or family of products, for *in situ* measurement of a critical physical, chemical or biological variable. Overall, 67.2% of the requirements were firm, while 22.2% were reasonable.

Definition Level

Figure 1. Definition level for the 454 requirements identified for water-related products

Relevance Level

The relevance level is a categorisation of the way in which the data is used within the product and the associated level of criticality. The vast majority of the requirements listed in the analysis were necessary for product generation, while a much smaller number of requirements are used for calibration and validation and supporting exploitation.

Relevance Level

Figure 2. Relevance level for the 454 requirements identified for water-related products

Criticality

The requirement criticality is the measure of the relevance of the requirement for the provision of reliable products and the vast majority of the requirements were identified as essential, meaning the product cannot exist without it.

Figure 3. Criticality level for the 454 requirements identified for water-related products

Barriers

The high level barriers initiate why a given *in situ* data requirement cannot be met for a given product. All requirements identified at least one barrier. The most common barrier was Accuracy (53.6% of requirements) while availability was an issue for 34.9% of products. Notably, cost, format, metadata and support were excluded since they were not found to be a high level barrier for any of the *in situ* requirements.

Figure 4. Number of requirements which have high level barriers

Compliance Level

Compliance level is a measure of how much the requirement is addressed by available data. Overall 59% of the *in situ* requirements within these water-related products have been met fully, while 39% were only partially met and 2% are unknown.

Compliance Level

Figure 5. Compliance level for the 454 requirements identified for water-related products

Datasets

For the Requirement groups 'Hydrology' and 'Hydrography', there were a total of **52 datasets** listed. These 52 datasets were used by a total of 94 products.

Figure 6. Pie chart showing the area in which the 52 datasets covered.

The *in situ* datasets which are most frequently used in current products are categorised as “Hydrographic network” and “Pan-European hydrological model”. For water quality, the most used *in situ* datasets are those “Water Colour and temperature ground data’ as shown in red in the Figure below (See Table S2 for full list).

Use of *in situ* data in existing Copernicus Products (Hydrology and Hydrogeography)

Figure 7. Use of *in situ* data in existing Copernicus Products as per data group.

2.3 The current role of Copernicus In Situ Component related to water

2.3.1 Previous analysis of Copernicus In Situ Component

This chapter summarises the water related data needs and gaps from previous project reports about this topic (COINS (Water Quality report; Global Hydrological In Situ Data report; Hydrological *In Situ* data requirements and availability reports) and H2020 Copernicus CAL/VAL solutions (CCVS) which evaluate the current Copernicus *in situ* Component. Both of those projects run in parallel with Water-ForCE, therefore they reflect a compatible and complementary set of ideas.

Table 3. *In situ* data gaps to solve the future needs for Copernicus In Situ Component, brought out COINS and Copernicus CAL/VAL solutions reports.

Water Quality	
Need	Gap
River water quality	The availability of water quality data at a regional or global level is generally driven by statutory monitoring requirements, which leads to relatively coarse measurements both temporally (e.g. monthly) and spatially.
Lake water quality	Current use of <i>in situ</i> data is based on traditional water quality monitoring that was not designed for the validation of satellite data. One challenge is the atmospheric correction of satellite imagery, where uncertainties exist even for the comparison with <i>in situ</i> data.
CAL/VAL absorption and scattering	Proper datasets of Lake water reflectances and Inherent Optical Properties (IOPs) are missing.
CAL the in-water algorithms, VAL in-water parameters	More relevant data of water constituents are needed

A future coastal service might also cover coastal lagoons	Relevant <i>in situ</i> data from Lagoons and other transitional systems are not available
Water Quantity	
Need	Gap
River flows	Limited access to the data from monitoring that is currently imposing the most significant limitations on data usage.
	There is no consistent access point for real-time river flow and level data on a global level.
Water level (lakes and rivers)	There is a lack of a global dataset of up-to-date <i>in situ</i> lake level measurements.
	For river levels, there are a number of limitations in the available <i>in situ</i> data, including data quality, lack of information on the technologies used and their uncertainties, lack of datum information, and undocumented shifts in datums due to flooding or subsidence. The time required to manually resolve the various data quality issues is prohibitive in many cases.
	The overall coverage is currently not ideal for validation, being limited in many areas and with a lack of extensive <i>in situ</i> measurements in any area.
Lake surface water temperature	There is a lack of off-shore temperature measurements, as well as a lack of metadata in relation to specific monitoring locations which can limit the usability of data.
Soil moisture	The principal gap is in the very limited number of soil moisture samples, particularly outside of the USA.
	The currently available data is inadequate for the proper validation of satellite soil moisture products over Europe, and most of the world.
Overall	
Need	Gap

Super sites	Fixed position sites (Towers or anchored buoys) are needed where low uncertainty measurements can be made regularly with auxiliary inherent optical properties measurements and regular water samples for water constituents' analyses
Site networks	Need for a network of measurements covering a variety of different water sites, both marine and lacustrine waters. As the most of the user interest is focused on waters that are close to inhabited areas, then this mostly includes complex coastal waters and inland waters.

2.3.2 Water-ForCE analysis of in situ data landscape: needs, gaps and solutions

The Water-ForCE analysis on *in situ* data needs is based on 2 different data sources: the outcomes of the relevant workshops run by Water-ForCE and the thorough technical analysis made by Water-ForCE Consortium grouped into 3 main topic: Water Quality, Water Quantity and Modelling.

The workshops organised in the framework of Water-ForCE aimed to collect opinions about the water related *in situ* and remote sensing data needs from experts, around the globe. We run 2 virtual workshops (Water-ForCE WP2-WP4 Workshop on *in situ* cal/val of satellite products of water quality and hydrology (17/5, 18/5 and 20/5/2021)), and additional surveys to gather external knowledge and experiences about the gaps and needs to improve the cooperation between RS and *in situ* water related activities. The outcomes of those workshops have been published in the Water-ForCE Zenodo community (Simis et al. 2021a; 2021b). Short summary of the collected results is presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Short summary outputs of the Water-ForCE *in situ* workshops and survey.

Water Quantity	
Gaps	Need
Data	Water level: accuracy of standard methods is suitable, but locations need to benefit EO cal/val.

	Water level: products in existence but data lacking for validation (satellite altimetry) - for large rivers globally.
	Water flow: data typically used for modelling - EU well covered, limited elsewhere.
	Soil moisture: need permanent <i>in situ</i> measurements, as well as campaigns. Capturing 3D nature of problem.
Coordination	Improve coordination of <i>in situ</i> measurements to fill observation gaps.
	Build support for long-term continuous measurements in countries that may not be able to afford to do so.
Funding	Seek support from WMO and others for guidance on use of technologies, and coordination and support to help make data available to international community and preservation.
	Focus on sustainability of funding for high quality measurements - e.g., use of Research Infrastructures.
Water Quality	
Gaps	Need
Data	Standardized data collection of different water related parameters: Phycocyanin and Phycoerythrin; Inherent Optical Properties; Turbidity; Coloured Dissolved Organic Matter; Chlorophyll-a; Total Suspended Solids / Total Suspended Matter / Suspended Particulate Matter; Secchi depth; Aquatic Vegetation; Primary Productivity; Nutrients; Optical backscattering
	Observation principles and techniques needs harmonization: Hyperspectral data; Vertical profiles; Representation of different water types, locations; Higher frequency and real-time measurements; Phytoplankton biomass proxies include fluorescence / biovolume / pigment concentration / absorption; Measurement / calibration standards; Quantification of uncertainties, observation gaps, precision; Registration of sensor drift.
	Pairing the hyperspectral radiometers with IOP and atmospheric sensors, additional cameras, and a weather station.

	Hyperspectral devices: Not all sites will directly benefit when adding those devices.
	Depth distributions: using profilers.
	Underwater spectrophotometers: which could measure in UV-Visible range
	An adequate CDOM (absorption) or fDOM (fluorescence) measurements.
Coordination	Integrating data from different sensors (drones, smartphones, ...).
	Provide QGIS tools that allow for cal/val using local data.
	Metadata, interoperability.
	Community-driven improvement of commercial sensor offering, e.g. radiometers, drones.
Funding	Low-cost versions of platforms and sensors.
	Low(er)-cost <i>in situ</i> absorption spectrometers should be improved to meet the usability of fluorescence probes, which would give way to broader use for algae pigment (e.g. chlorophyll-a) monitoring.
	Leverage human effort - citizen science (learn from other industries, e.g. medical).

The following table (Table 5) presents the outcomes of Water-ForCE technical analysis related to *in situ* data needs based on the results of the work of the technical WPs (Water Quality, Water Quantity and Modelling) and what solutions WP4 was offering to cover those needs.

Table 5. Summary of *in situ* data needs and proposed solutions in Water-ForCE deliverables (Purpose: C/V: Calibration and Validation of satellite products, AD: Algorithm development; MD: Model development).

WP/ Del	Subject Action Type	<i>In situ</i> data detected NEED	Purpose
WP 2	WATER QUALITY		
D2.2		Recommendations on Copernicus products - Water Quality	

	<p>Coordination Data Gap</p>	<p>A water quality database with metadata and quality-controlled data available for satellite EO algorithm developers. Open water data (away from shore) for Chla, TSM and turbidity at global scale.</p>	<p>AD</p>
	<p>Coordination Data Gap</p>	<p>Training for collecting this type of data (useful for remote sensing calibration and validation). Time series of water quality data to match-up with satellite overpass, including key variables, strategic locations.</p>	<p>C/V</p>
	<p>Coordination Data Manag</p>	<p>Common vocabulary between <i>in situ</i> water quality community and remote sensing community. informed by existing services (NERC vocabulary services, GLEON/NETLAKE common vocabulary, CF conventions, EDMO codes).</p>	<p>C/V</p>
	<p>Coordination Data Gap</p>	<p>Wider collection of hyperspectral radiometry (from fixed autonomous stations and ad hoc). Radiometric observations to validate the water-leaving reflectance product are particularly lacking.</p>	<p>C/V</p>
D2.3		Atmospheric correction	
	<p>Data Gap</p>	<p>Transect spectroradiometric data to assess the adjacency effect, particularly for small water bodies.</p>	<p>C/V - AD</p>
	<p>Data Gap</p>	<p>Optical data such as lake water reflectances and Inherent Optical Properties (IOPs) needed for calibrating and validating the</p>	<p>C/V - AD</p>

		atmospheric correction algorithm(s) and optical processes in the water (absorption and scattering).	
	Data Gap	Full uncertainty budget needed for reflectance measurements	C/V - AD
	Data Gap	Data from more regions and optical water types are required (marine and inland)	C/V - AD
	Coordination Data Gap	Need for AC round robin exercises with focus on validation of adjacency effect correction using <i>in situ</i> data for validation	C/V - AD
	Coordination Data Manag.	Need for networks with centralized services (data calibration, handling, reduction, processing, quality control, uncertainty, archiving, distribution).	C/V - AD
	Coordination	Need for standardization of network components such as instruments, measurement protocols, and processing.	C/V - AD
D2.4		Higher-level biogeochemical products	
	Data Gap	For continued development of detection methods, specific efforts to collect <i>in situ</i> reference observations are required	C/V - AD
D2.5		Technical needs for future Sentinels	
	Data Gap	<i>In situ</i> measurements of reflectance are required for the inter-comparison and the synergistic exploitation of the current and expected satellite missions. Along	C/V -AD

		with traditional field campaigns and cruises, an increasing number of autonomous hyperspectral radiometers, including those that can be operated on ferries (Qin et al., 2017; Brando et al., 2016), have been proved to support qualification of satellite data (e.g., Braga et al., 2022).	
WP 3	WATER QUANTITY		
D3.3		Copernicus products and services - water management	
	Data Gap	Validation of retrievals, and potentially calibration of the models are vital. Unfortunately, this is not done as comprehensively as needed due to the lack of <i>in situ</i> data.	C/V
	Data Gap	Standardized uncertainty assessments are necessary for both remote sensing indicators and <i>in situ</i> data	C/V
D3.4		Water resources modelling	
	Data Gap	<i>In situ</i> data is highly needed to better explain the bathymetry of the waterbodies	C/V - MD
	Data Gap	There is a growing interest in better integration of RS with <i>in situ</i> soil moisture data. The collection of soil moisture data is recent (e.g. international soil moisture network) and has not been used a lot to complement/evaluate soil moisture data from remote sensing.	AD - MD

WP 5	MODELLING	
D5.1		Copernicus EO needs for modellers and decision makers
	<p>Coordination Data Gap</p>	<p>Make RS and <i>in situ</i> datasets comparable. All Copernicus services are mainly used for calibration and validation of models while the main limitations users have in using them for modelling are data quality as compared with quality of regular <i>in situ</i> measurements. The most important thing for the users is to improve the Remote Sensing data quality and reduce the uncertainty.</p>
D5.3		AI for accurately correcting systematic forecast errors
	<p>Data Gap</p>	<p>Bottlenecks implementing AI: An important aspect of ML is the availability of sufficient training datasets which increases the quality of the algorithms and results overall. For instance, for water quality assessment, the ML needs sufficient <i>in situ</i> data which is often not available. Method performance assessment needs benchmark datasets with known and verified outcome.</p>
D5.4		Integration of satellite EO and modelling
	<p>Coordination</p>	<p>Introduction of RS/Copernicus data in national water management. Demonstrator applications with</p>

		merged data from <i>in situ</i> networks and RS/Copernicus sources are needed. Examples from countries where these approaches have been applied (Finland) need to be shared and replicated.	
WP 4	Aligning <i>In situ</i> and EO - SOLUTIONS TO THE PREVIOUS NEEDS		
D2.2	Funding	Costs for automated measurements should be reduced to allow larger scale data collection.	
	Funding	Funding opportunities for installing spectroradiometers in the existing infrastructures.	
	Funding	Dedicated field campaigns and data sharing arrangements needed throughout EU funding programs	
D2.3	Funding	Promote sustained long-term funding (instead of project-based short-term funding) to support data providers for network, infrastructure, data collection, Q&A and training.	
D5.3	Coordination	Creating validated <i>in situ</i> data or dataset builders to create ready-to-use training datasets (i.e., <i>in situ</i> and satellite data pairing) might help AI researchers which might not have EO expertise to create more advanced AI/ML methods.	
D5.3	Coordination	Establish standard validation protocols to clean <i>in situ</i> datasets. These could be included in the current DIAS platform in the form of notebooks/tutorials/SOPs	

D5.4	Coordination	<p>Closer cooperation between RS/ Copernicus services and national water monitoring organizations. Such cooperative activities need to go beyond concerns related to the importance of <i>in situ</i> water monitoring networks for calibration and validation of satellite-based products. Joint engagement in local water management (in research and in operations), where usage of merged data will bring value is needed bringing in the advantages of both approaches.</p>	
D4.2		<p><i>In situ</i> data-intensive monitoring. SOP and methodological aspects of <i>in situ</i> data gathering for RS</p>	
	Coordination	<p>No major gaps are currently identified as regards selection of protocols, intercalibration methods, and quality control, because examples from dedicated research campaigns guided by existing protocols already exist. Instead, expansion of these efforts is the major improvement which is now needed. <i>In situ</i> observation, remote sensing and modelling communities should work together to identify sites which show the largest potential to fill current data gaps, in order to justify the required investment.</p>	

	<p>Coordination Funding</p>	<p>There is a clear need to coordinate collection and sharing of high-frequency data, particularly where these fall outside the scope of the hydrological monitoring networks, which are largely organised under WMO activities.</p> <p>The burden, in terms of time/cost and expertise required, of setting up data services and disseminating these through discovery services is significant. Technical support should be provided to ensure common standards are followed, to secure data for the future, and to make the data easily discoverable. As the standards evolve, the FAIR principles will be increasingly met, to the point that data discovery starts from a standard web search. However, this evolution requires investment into new and existing repositories and financial support for centralized, coordinating bodies to keep data records relevant.</p>	
<p>D4.4</p>		<p>Uptake for alternative monitoring methods [Usability for <i>in situ</i> data for EO]</p>	
	<p>Coordination Data Manag.</p>	<p>Create a centralized data access and curated dataset for alternative data sources (UAV data, Citizen science, Low-cost sensors networks), including a portal for UAV imagery data sharing.</p>	

	Coordination	Coordinate and stimulate the engagement to local communities and stakeholders for the adoption of these alternative data sources, as a source of <i>in situ</i> data	
D4.5		[<i>In situ</i> data needs for] Development of New Higher Level products combining EO and <i>In situ</i> data	
	Coordination Data Manag. Funding	<p>Still, to get the best possible new products in case of reliability and accuracy, both <i>in situ</i> and remote sensing networks should work together.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the <i>in situ</i> data collection would happen at the appropriate time (e.g. close to the satellite overpass and with clear weather), so that collected datasets would be also usable for remote sensing studies. - to increase the reliability and accuracy of both <i>in situ</i> and remote sensing monitoring results, more frequent data collection is needed. This can be achieved using more automated monitoring systems in water bodies. - HFM systems should be also equipped with exactly those sensors (e.g. fDOM, CO₂, reflectance) which variables 	

		<p>are needed to build up the offered new higher-level products, and if possible also with a sensor for global irradiance and reflectance measurements.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - All those datasets should be made openly available following the FAIR principles, so they could be used for all possible communities (e.g. for calibrating their products). 	
D4.6		<i>In situ</i> Data Management for EO: Standardization and Open Science	
	<p>Coordination Data Manag. Funding</p>	<p>Continuity of databases (Long term data storage) and the associated metadata. No single organization responsible (e.g. Copernicus In Situ Component, EEA, ESA) = no proper funding and data continuity. Define the role of EEA, Copernicus In Situ Component, Copernicus 'Water', as centralized body for EU to store and make data available</p>	
	<p>Coordination Funding</p>	<p>Build a common infrastructure for data storage/sharing. Repurpose global data centers for EO, allow data producers to provide and update data, providing benefits to data providers such as QA/QC services</p>	
	<p>Coordination</p>	<p>Identify who should/could be responsible for coordinating and funding for data sharing/storing</p>	

Figure 8. Analysis of the solutions given by Water-ForCE deliverables related to the type of action needed to be taken

Coordination arises as the main action needed to solve the needs (11 actions), followed by proper funding schemes (8 actions) and lastly data management actions (3 actions), for the *in situ* Component of the Copernicus Programme for Water. All the needs and gaps can be briefly summarised in 4 main topics, which may be solved by a set of 4 actions that can lead to the desired solutions (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Graphic analysis of the paired need and action towards solution.

2.4 Water-ForCE specific recommendations for Copernicus In Situ Component

To summarise the analysis presented in Sections 3, Water-ForCE make the following two recommendations:

1. Standardised methods and requirements for data collection - to better align *in situ* data collection also with the needs for satellite EO
2. Choose (according to the Optical Water Types) and suggest existing (nicely equipped) sites (preferable long-term sites; both river, lake and coastal) to establish permanent SUPERSITES for global Copernicus water related products (similar also possible for soil moisture studies)
 - Standardised methods and requirements for data collection
 - Automated water-reflectance measurements on those sites (if does not exist yet)
 - Copernicus programme needs to support financially data collection on those sites
 - All data (also raw data from automated measurements) will be sent and stored to Copernicus In Situ Component (e.g. EEA) with the required metadata
 - All QA/QC data will be shared (made openly available) according to the FAIR principles through Copernicus In Situ Component (e.g. EEA)

3. Part 2 - Review of external in-situ data repositories

In this section, external in situ data repositories are reviewed. Data repositories can be evaluated in terms of 1) the intended purpose of the repository and the funding set-up, 2) the data providers/producers, 3) the interface between the data providers and the repository, 4) the content and structure of the repository, 5) the interface between the repository and the end-users, and 6) the intended end-users (Figure 10).

Figure 10. Schematic showing the database characteristics considered in this report and the process from data providers to the end data users.

The optimum organisation and storage of in-situ data for use with satellite-EO depends on the exact application and the rapid development of remote sensing practices. However, an optimum system may include some of the following conditions:

- Purpose: Repository is well-known, and clearly contains inland/coastal in-situ data for use with satellite-EO data
- Funding: Repository has sustainably funding (e.g., 10+ years guaranteed)
- Data producers/providers: Data are provided by single or multiple producers who are motivated to keep their data in the repository and are aligned/harmonised with the use of the data. Data are high-quality and producers are trustable
- Content:
 - All key in-situ reference data are available including water-leaving reflectance, water quality and water quantity
 - Good metadata and unique identifiers
 - Temporal/spatial representation to match with satellite data
 - Standardised formatting
 - International/Transboundary datasets
 - In-situ data can be matched-up with satellite overpasses, or datasets are already matched-up
 - Data are published in a timely manner
 - Data can be added or updated
- End users:
 - Repository is open-access and limits the barriers to new users
 - Allows download

- Data are well-known or a metabase facilitates the discoverability
- Machine-readable
- Terms of use / acknowledgement practises ect
- User guide and support is provided in some form
- Technical:
 - Data are stored in a sustainable way and at a reasonable cost
 - Repository is structurally good

A list of existing in-situ data repositories and databases were compiled by the consortium group (Table 6). When discussed collectively we will call them in-situ data repositories. All include at least some observed water quality, water quantity data from inland or coastal water bodies. These in-situ data are either currently, or could in the future be used in satellite-EO data processing. Repositories which were conceived and managed within Europe are of particular focus, however some particularly well-known databases from outside of the EU were included.

Table 6. Characteristics of in-situ repositories including water quantity and water quality data from inland and coastal areas.

Water - ForCE

	Concept		Provider					Content					Access															
	Data focus	Intended community	Metadata repository	Data Repository Database	Continuous	Soft	EU-based	Open upload*	Project	Monitoring program	Mixed (open)	Mixed (managed)	Includes EU data	Water quality	Water quantity	Water leaving refl.	Lakes	Rivers	Coastal / Oceans	National	Regional	Global	Download*	Help contact	API			
AERONET-OC	Ocean	Sat-EO	●	●	●		●	●				●	●	●	●	●	●	●				●	●	●	●	●	https://aeronet.gsfc.nasa.gov	
CUAHSI Hydroshare	Environmental	Reserachers	●	●	●		●	●			●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●				●	●	●	●	●	https://hydroshare.org
Danube Basin Water Quality	Regional monitoring	Management	●	●	●		●	●		●		●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●				●	●	●	●	●	https://www.icpdr.org/wq-db
EMSO ERIC	Ocean	Sat-EO	●	●	●	●	●	●				●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●				●	●	●	●	●	https://data.emso.eu
EDI	Environmental	Reserachers	●	●	●		●	●			●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●				●	●	●	●	●	https://portal.edirepository.org
GEMStat Data Portal	Global monitoring	Public/researchers	●	●	●		●	●			●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●				●	●	●	●	●	https://gemstat.org
GEOSS Portal	Environmental	Sat-EO	●	●	●		●	●			●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●				●	●	●	●	●	https://www.geoportal.org
GRDC	Runoff	General (?)	●	●	●		●	●			●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●				●	●	●	●	●	https://portal.grdc.bafg.de
HydroSHEDS	Hydrology	General (?)	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●		●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●				●	●	●	●	●	https://hydrosheds.org
ISIMIP	Temp and met	Modellers	●	●	●		●	●	●	●		●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●				●	●	●	●	●	https://data.isimip.org
KNB	Environmental	Reserachers	●	●	●		●	●	●	●		●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●				●	●	●	●	●	https://knb.ecoinformatics.org
LIMNADES	Inland and coastal	Sat-EO	●	●	●		●	●	●	●		●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●				●	●	●	●	●	https://limnades.stir.ac.uk
MONOCLE	Inland and coastal	Sat-EO / in-situ	●	●	●		●	●	●	●		●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●				●	●	●	●	●	https://monocle-h2020.eu
NETLAKE	Lakes	In-situ	●	●	●		●	●	●	●		●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●				●	●	●	●	●	https://dkit.ie/netlake
OLA: Observatory on LAKes	Regional monitoring	Management	●	●	●		●	●	●	●		●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●				●	●	●	●	●	https://si-ola.inrae.fr/si_lacs
PANGAEA	Environmental	Reserachers	●	●	●		●	●	●	●		●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●				●	●	●	●	●	https://www.pangaea.de
SeabASS:	Ocean	Sat-EO	●	●	●		●	●	●	●		●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●				●	●	●	●	●	https://seabass.gsfc.nasa.gov
Vannmiljø (Norway)	National monitoring	Management	●	●	●		●	●	●	●		●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●				●	●	●	●	●	https://vannmiljo.miljodirektoratet.no
VISS (Sweden)	National monitoring	Management	●	●	●		●	●	●	●		●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●				●	●	●	●	●	https://viss.lansstyrelsen.se
Water Quality Archive (UK)	National monitoring	Management	●	●	●		●	●	●	●		●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●				●	●	●	●	●	https://environment.data.gov.uk
Waterbase (EEA)	National monitoring	Management	●	●	●		●	●	●	●		●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●				●	●	●	●	●	https://eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps
Waterinfo (Belgium)	National monitoring	Management	●	●	●		●	●	●	●		●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●				●	●	●	●	●	https://waterinfo.be
WISA (Austria)	National monitoring	Management	●	●	●		●	●	●	●		●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●				●	●	●	●	●	https://info.bml.gv.at
Zenodo	Environmental	Reserachers	●	●	●		●	●	●	●		●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●				●	●	●	●	●	https://zenodo.org

* Brackets indicate that email or login is required to access open data or that help contact is an email address

3.1 Repository Purpose

Four key groups were identified for data repositories, in terms of the intended purpose. These were 1) monitoring schemes, 2) project-based, 3) open repositories with mixed data sources, and 4) open repositories with managed or harmonised data sources. Two additional relevant groups were identified, which were metadata repositories and project-based databases rather than repositories. These groups are summarised in the section below.

3.1.1 Project-based repositories

Research projects or short-term programs often require a designated space to store the input and output data of the project. We include six examples of project-based repositories, including MONOCLE (<https://monocle-h2020.eu/Data>) and LIMNADES (<https://limnades.stir.ac.uk>), which were both fully or partially funded by Horizon2020 and were concerned with enhancing the use of in-situ inland and coastal data within EO-based water quality services. Project-based repositories typically receive funding until the project ends, or are funded by the institute's data management/storage budget and may not be included in the proposal at all. The management of project-based repositories may vary including persons within the project or database management team from the institute.

3.1.2 Monitoring scheme repositories

Monitoring schemes, at the national or regional level, often have open repositories and sometimes data portals. Data may be collected for the Water Framework Directive or other legislation. This report included nine national and regional monitoring schemes, including the European Environment Agencies Waterbase repository. Repositories designed to store data from national or regional monitoring schemes have some specific requirements. In particular, they are designed for upload only by designated parties within the scheme. Data within a monitoring scheme may be more harmonised, in terms of collection methods and metadata etc, although this is not necessarily always the case. An additional specificity is that they may be designed to have regular data uploads or updates. Many national or regional monitoring repositories do not allow public download, or data are only available on email request and a data catalogue may not be published. Funding for monitoring scheme repositories is often continuous and a

dedicated person or team may be responsible for curating and managing datasets and the repository.

3.1.3 Open data repositories

Open data repositories are those which are entirely open for upload and download, usually within a certain thematic topic. These repositories include Zenodo, Environmental Data Initiative (hereafter “EDI”) and CUASHI Hydroshare (hereafter “Hydroshare”). These repositories can differ in the degree of openness. For example, there are typically limitations on how much data you can upload as an individual or a single project. Additionally, EDI in particular requires you to contact them via email to determine if your data are appropriate for the site, and they prioritize work from within the related scientific community. In contrast, Zenodo and Hydroshare can be done just through their online portal. These repositories typically have continuous funding. One clear benefit is that there is no need to manage data use or ownership, since by publishing the data, the authors specify the terms of use. However, they store massive amounts of data, either on a dedicated server or cloud, which has substantial cost. Moreover, they require large investment into software development and maintenance of the website itself. Existing open-access international repositories included in our analysis were funded by research and innovation related government bodies. These may have thematic requirements, for example, data may be only environmental research data. These repositories are also suitable for small projects to store their data and make it available for re-use, by allowing it to be published.

3.1.4 Open managed data repositories

Another important class of repository is open repositories, which have a degree of data management and harmonisation. The repositories included in this group are AERONET-OC, GEMstat, Global Runoff Data Portal, and PANGAEA. These databases are different to open repositories as the result is a more curated data product, although there is some crossover with monitoring schemes (Section 2.1) and open data repositories (Section 2.3). For example, PANGAEA allows open upload of data from different providers, similar to an open data repository but has a data editorial team which “maintain the integrity and authenticity of the

data” (<https://www.pangaea.de/>). Similarly, GEMstat requires the voluntary participation of monitoring schemes from around the world, but attempts to harmonise the data post-collection to provide a map-based water quality tool (<https://gemstat.org/>). These repositories offer open-access download in most cases, but some datasets may require additional requests. Such repositories require continuous funding and data management resources.

3.1.5 Metadata repositories

Metadata repositories are repositories that store metadata and can be used for data discovery. The metadata repositories included in this report were EMSO ERIC data portal to direct users to EMSO observatory data based on location, the GEOSS portal designed with EO-users in mind, and NETLAKE which is a metadata repository for high-frequency lake monitoring data. Metadata repositories vary in their data scope and intended user. They also vary in their funding and whether they are one-off projects or if they are actively maintained. While metadata repositories do not have to store the actual data, they do have to provide relevant metadata and links to the datasets themselves, in order to be useful. Maintenance can be automated or manual or a hybrid. For example, NETLAKE was a manual database put together by the lake monitoring community, while the GEOSS portal links end-users to EO and in-situ data while using automated updating, where links are checked and some metadata are automatically populated from data websites (See D4.5 for more on GEOSS portal).

3.1.6 Project-based databases

Finally, some relevant in-situ datasets are stored in databases (rather than repositories - see definitions section above). Smaller projects, for example, might require a single database that can be uploaded on an open repository such as EDI or Hydroshare. There are many such databases, which can be found through open data repositories or metadata repositories. Two examples included here are the European Multi Lake Survey dataset containing biogeochemical parameters collected from 100+ lakes over 2018 (<https://portal.edirepository.org/nis/mapbrowse?packageid=edi.176.5>; Mantzouki et

al., 2018) and the Global dataset of long-term summertime vertical temperature profiles from 153 lakes (<https://portal.edirepository.org/nis/mapbrowse?scope=edi&identifier=705>; Pilla et al., 2022) which are both stored on EDI as single Data Packages. Another example is The Surface Water Chemistry (SWatCH) database which comprises data from various sources but has been standardized into one high-quality transboundary database (Rotteveel et al., 2022) stored on Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6484939>).

3.2 Data scope

Only two of the repositories were designed specifically to store inland or coastal data, and they were MONOCLE and LIMNADES repositories (Spyrakos et al., 2020). Three repositories (AERONET-OC, EMSO ERIC, and SeaBASS) were ocean focused but included a small number of lake or coastal monitoring sites. A few repositories were very wide in scope, and were classified as concerned with environmental data at large, which includes some inland and coastal data (Hydroshare, EDI, KNB, Zenodo). The largest proportion of the databases have a water-body monitoring focus in a specific region. These included OLA, Danube basin water quality portal, Vannmiljø (Norway), VISS (Sweden), Water Quality Archive (England), Waterbase (EEA), Waterinfo (Belgium), WISA (Austria).

3.3 Intended users

A few of the repositories were designed specifically for the EO-data user community; PANGAEA, MONOCLE, LIMNADES and the GEOSS portal. A greater number were designed for research in general, or the in-situ data user community. Most spatially oriented repositories are assumed to be designed for the management of water-bodies and environmental monitoring of that region. This could include EO-users but not primarily.

3.4 Funding

Funding is particularly important when considering the scope of the viability of a repository and the longevity of it. Funding can include the expense involved in the development, curation and maintenance of the repository. It may also include hosting, storage and server costs, a designated team and help-contact.

All the repositories were largely supported by public funding. In general, detailed information on the amount and source of funding received by each repository was limited, however two basic groups were identified. This was whether the repository had continuous or soft funding. Of the repositories, most (14 repositories) received funding for the foreseeable future, which was considered continuous (Table 1). A minority of 6 repositories (Table 1), were soft-funded, meaning they received short-term funding, for example from a 3-year project, or were no longer receiving any formal funding.

Monitoring schemes, open data and managed open data repositories were mostly continuously funded. Regional and national monitoring schemes are largely funded by government-based bodies, such as the European Environment Agency (EEA), or the Environment Agency (EA) in England and Wales. Open data and managed open data repositories are typically funded by Research and Innovation oriented international groups. For example Zenodo which is funded by the EU OpenAire projects, or GEMstat which was funded through the United Nations Environment Program (UNEP). Different levels of visibility are associated with each repository, and it is beyond the scope of this document to fully evaluate this. Some databases, for example GEMstat, have expressed 'insufficient funding' as a problem (GEMs/Water, 2019).

In contrast, project-based repositories were typically soft-funded. Discussion with data managers and experts highlighted various scenarios related to soft-funded repositories. For example, once the project funding is suspended the database or repository can be abandoned regardless of how widely used it is. Alternatively, as in the case of the LIMNADES repository, the maintenance may be taken up by the residing institution from goodwill, or the time of unpaid former project participants. In such cases, there may be little investment in the continued growth of the repository. Soft-funded repositories may also become unviable if the software becomes out of date and there is insufficient funding to update it.

Notably, in academic contexts, data maintenance is not always covered by research funding. For example, in German institutions database management and repository curation is typically the responsibility of the academic institution and is not funded by third-party funds.

3.5 Data providers

Open access repositories typically allow data to be freely uploaded and hence the data provider could be anyone. There were eight repositories included which allowed open upload. All these still require some regulation on uploads, for example, the data provider must make an account for identification and provide some specific information about the data. Some data repositories have limitations on the storage and the length of time that data will be stored. Some repositories also require a manual screening process, such as EDI, where data providers are requested to email first and certain research affiliations are prioritised. When uploading data, it is possible to stipulate the terms of use, but anyone can access the data and there is less control for the data provider.

For other repositories, the collection, upload and repository management are conducted within the same operation. This can be the case for some national monitoring schemes (e.g. Water Quality Archive gov.uk). Some project-based repositories also have cohesive collection, upload and storage (e.g. MONOCLE), or if the data were not collected by the repository operation itself, it may have been actively gathered, processed and uploaded by members of the project (e.g., ISIMIP, LIMNADES). In some cases, data providers want to protect or limit the access to their data, for example, to ensure the providers have the first opportunity of publication or to prohibit overlapping projects.

3.6 Data provider interface

Data providers can vary in expertise, resources and intentions. Hence, their needs from a repository can differ. The interface between the data provider and the repository determines the process of data upload, and the level of regulation and support during this process. Requirements for providing data can include metadata and interoperability standards (discussed in the later section 3.7.8 and

in Deliverable D4.2), and quality assurance and quality control (QAQC). Support offered to data providers can include: a help email or chat link, manual data handling and completeness checks, automated data handling tools and a designated management person/team to oversee the data upload and documentation.

Typically, open data repositories, such as Zenodo and Hydroshare, just provide the storage space and recommendation on metadata. In such cases, the data quality and documentation are the responsibility of the provider. Both repositories provide a technical help desk. Repositories such as EDI, GEMstat or PANGAEA can provide an additional level of support in terms of data harmonisation, metadata completeness checks or even manually check the data. In project-based databases, such as ISIMIP (lake sector) and LIMNADES, data was gathered in a one-off data call and they requested specific metadata to be provided with the observed data. In some cases, the project would also facilitate this process, or QAQC the data. It is not easy to assess data repositories where there is a closed upload process.

3.7 Repository content

Note that, since the report does not contain an exhaustive list of repositories, the values and percentages given here are only reflective of our sample group of repositories, and are not necessarily reflective of all relevant repositories or data at large.

3.7.1 Variables

Key in-situ variables for coupling with satellite-EO based data are water quantity, water quality (divided into biogeochemical data, and direct or derived radiometric quantities). None of the databases considered in this report included all three types of data. Of the repositories, 17 included water quantity and 13 included water quality. Only five repositories included direct or derived radiometric quantities, which are essential for improving and validating atmospheric correction, and validating water quality products (D2.2).

3.7.2 Water-bodies considered

Coverage of inland waters is very important, including lakes, rivers and coastal areas. Of the list of repositories investigated in this report, 20 include data from lakes. However, the number of lakes varied from just 3 lakes in the AERONET-OC repository, to more than 1000 lakes in the GEMstat database. Rivers and coastal data were also well represented within the data repositories that were considered, both present in 19 repositories. It is not known whether this is reflective of all data repositories since that would require an exhaustive analysis.

3.7.3 Spatial scope

All of the repositories that were assessed included data from European water bodies, as a criterion for the original search. Overall, 4 repositories included only data from one country (Norway, Sweden, England, Belgium and Austria), 7 repositories included data across a region and 13 repositories considered a global scope. Global data repositories do not necessarily include an even distribution globally but have no spatial constraints.

3.7.4 Temporal scope

The repositories included in the analysis had various temporal ranges depending on the dataset. Some data repositories, particularly water quantity data repositories, store long-term datasets, such as GRDC which includes data starting from 1806. OLA, EDI, and ISIMIP all store long-term datasets including around 50-60 years of monitoring data. Direct and datasets were shorter in temporal scope. LIMNADES contains data from 1990 to 2021. AERONET-OC and SeaBASS contain ~20 years of data.

Another consideration in temporal scope is the timeliness of data upload, following its collection. This largely depends on the condition in which the data are uploaded (e.g. is raw data uploaded), whether there is any embargo on the data (e.g. a period where the data are not open-access), and the speed/resources attributed to data processing and upload.

3.7.5 Database types

The typically preferred data format is data table data in TAB-delimited or excel files, which are presented in a relational database. NetCDF files were also possible and some Shape files (e.g. HydroATLAS).

3.7.6 Versions and updates

Repositories use different practices for data versioning and updating. Some repositories require each dataset to have multiple timestamps, e.g. MONOCLE include multiple timestamps with each dataset, for the collection of the data, the processing of the data, the ingestion of the data. This allows raw data to be uploaded, and different levels of processing. Some repositories just upload one version of the data. Once published repositories may not allow data to be edited or updated.

3.7.7 Unique identifiers

Unique identifiers allow data to be uniquely named and reduce the possibility of duplication. Various different unique identifiers exist including ARK, DOI, PURL, URL, UUID. All of the in-situ databases explored in this study use unique identifiers, typically DOI's. This creates some transparency and traceability in terms of what the data are and how they can be found again. Open repositories such as Hydroshare or Zenodo etc assign a DOI automatically. Repositories themselves can also have unique identifiers if they meet sufficient standards, for example, the Re3 standard which includes Pangaea, Zenodo, EDI and Hydroshare.

3.7.8 Metadata

Metadata are data about the data and are required to interpret the data. Various independent sources provide well defined protocols for metadata in general, and for scientific variables. Some specific examples of metadata standards include ISO 19115, CSDGM, ANZLIC, GEODCAT, Ckan. There is no specific formalised metadata scheme for incorporating in-situ data into satellite-EO products.

AERONET-OC and SeaBASS provide guides for recording data with metadata for match-up with satellite data. Additionally, LIMNADES metadata were conceived by the GEO AquaWatch group of satellite-EO specialists with particular focus on future use with inland EO water quality products. The product of this collaboration was the LIMNADES metadata template which includes metadata for stationary measuring stations in general (Table 7) and for the different variables ranging from biogeochemical variables such as phytoplankton abundance, to water leaving radiance (Table 8). It is clear that spectral data, shown in Table 8., requires a substantially higher amount of metadata and information on the methodology used. Notably, not all in-situ observations are matched-up to the same time and geographical location as remote sensing data, although this is not always necessary. Seabass was the only repository that includes match-up datasets.

Table 7. List of metadata required for monitoring stations in the LIMNADES repository.

Essential	Desirable
Unique code to identify your station	Individuals/contact involved in data collection
The primary email contact address	Institution samples were collected on behalf of
First time recorded at station	Name of cruise data were collected on
Initial latitude position	Name of project data were collected for
Initial longitude position	Funding body or institution
	Last time recorded at station
	Final latitude position
	Final longitude position
	Description of weather and measured wind speed, Air temperature
	Observed wave height, Observed cloud cover, Air pressure,
	Measured water depth
	Water temperature at surface
	Water clarity with secchi depth
	Name of inland or coastal water body

Table 8. Metadata required for data submission in the LIMNADES database, described for each variable. Spectral data is shown in red.

		Pigments	Dissolved element fraction	Suspended matter	Water temperature	Salinity	Turbidity	Absorption coefficients	Scattering coefficients	Radiometric quantity	Derived radiometric quantity	Particle size distribution	Aerosol optical thickness	Phytoplankton abundance
ID	Identification code	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•
Methodology information	Link to extraction protocol or paper	•	•					•						
	Analytical method used	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•
	Calculation computation method								•	•				
	Calibration history								•	•				
	Full name of analytical instrument	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•
	Link to calibration or assurance report								•					
	Processing protocol								•					
	List any correction details							•						
	List any processing methods							•						
	Serial number of instrument	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•
	Length of time it took before storage	•	•					•						
	Temperature the same was stored at	•	•					•						
	Was correction for straylight applied?									•	•			
	Was self shading correction applied?									•	•			
	Was sun zenith angle taken into account?									•	•			
	Was the sample fixed or fresh?							•						
	Was tilt sensor calibration performed?									•	•			
	Were dark measurements performed?									•	•			
Were Immersion coefficients taken into account?									•	•				
What was used as a reference value							•							
Instrument metadata	Average latitude for all measurements									•				
	Average longitude for all measurements									•				
	Depth at which the sample was taken	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•
	Depth of measurement							•		•	•			
Field information	Instrument timestamp for each measurement									•				
	Depth at which the sample was taken	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•
Data	Method used to sample	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•
	Number of spectra used in aggregation									•				
	Pigment name	•												
	Standard deviation for aggregated measurements									•	•	•	•	
	The absolute uncertainty associated with the value	•	•	•	•	•	•	•						
	The value recorded by the instrument	•	•	•	•	•	•	•						
	The value recorded by the instrument at a specific bin							•						
	The wavelength bins recorded by instrument							•	•	•	•	•	•	•
	Type of measurement		•	•										
	Type of uncertainty associated with value	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•
Units of bins							•	•	•	•	•	•	•	
Units of measurement	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	
Data Sharing	The chosen data policy	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•
	The date for licenced data (C-F) to be made open access	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•

3.7.9 Storage

Data storage can be very expensive and consume a lot of energy. The two main storage options are cloud-based and dedicated servers. Typically, dedicated servers are more appropriate for larger repositories, although cloud-based storage can be more accessible and reduce the needs of a data manager, including back-ups and security. There is a very large range in storage capacity between the repositories included in this report. For example, LIMNADES repository is a total of 50 GB while Zenodo offers 50 GB per dataset and has an unlimited number of datasets. It also has 100 petabytes of space (<https://help.zenodo.org/>).

3.8 End-user interface

3.8.1 Findability

Findability refers to how easily a potential user can find or discover the data and whether there is sufficient information to interpret the data products. This can determine whether the data will be found and used correctly. Findability is one of the key variables of the FAIR protocol, which stipulates that data should be easy to find by both computers and humans. Key considerations in evaluating this include the discovery metadata standards used, whether there is a catalogue explaining the data services, key words to facilitate searching and retrieval, and the visibility of the repository; e.g. in Google search, in publications.

There were large differences between the findability of the data repositories explored. The open repositories, such as Zenodo and Hydroshare are very easy to find in general, and have their own search engines that use the metadata and keywords of each data package to search for relevant data. Hence, the findability depends on how comprehensive and relevant the metadata and keywords are. Moreover, the GEOSS portal typically links up. Individual databases/packages can also be found using Google search domain.

More harmonised data repositories offer map-based browsers for data exploration prior to download. These include MONOCLE, GEMStat and EMSO ERIC, which have map-based web-browsers, allowing some degree of data exploration and

catalogue. Some of the repositories require an account to be made before accessing the data catalogue or metadata, such as Danube Basin Water Quality portal and LIMNADES.

3.8.2 Downloading data & data permission

The procedure to download data varied between the repositories. All repositories (excluding the metadata repositories) allow open-access download. Of the repositories, 14 were fully open, meaning there was no requirement of a login to download at least some of the data, but there may still be terms and conditions. The other 8 data repositories require some identification or additional regulation. For some of the repositories this is just a login account but it may also mean that data providers need to approve each request for download, which is the case for LIMNADES repository. In some cases there are data which are not open-access, for example PANGAEA. Download limitations are also typical but depend on the repository.

3.8.3 Help support

Repositories have different approaches to supporting end-users to download and interpret data. This can include the instructions provided to new users on how to download data, and the provision of a live or email-based help contact. Even where data are available for download, it can be inaccessible due to the complexity of the process and lack of educational resources.

Overall, ten repositories were found to have an explicit help contact, help form, or a forum for posting questions. None of the databases had a live chat. The responsiveness of contact emails is not measured. Some repositories provide email contacts for general information (e.g. GEOSS portal and LIMNADES) but it is not clear if these emails are responsive to end-user help support. Other repositories provided substantial support documentation, videos and FAQ's, for example ISIMIP and PANGAEA.

3.8.4 Download and machine-readability

Some databases support the retrieval of their content via API (Application programming interface) which enables the data to be machine-readable. Ways to do this include a simple open search implementation or interface such as RESTful (REpresentational State Transfer). Machine-readable data repositories allow in-situ data to be retrieved regularly or to check for updated data (i.e. a new version of data) which would be necessary if in-situ data are to be assimilated into water quality satellite-EO data services. More than half of the data repositories have an API, but a substantial proportion did not have an API or had insufficient information on the website to determine this. Metadata repositories such as GEOSS were not machine-readable but it is not necessary as they do not store the desired data themselves (see D4.5 for more details on GEOSS portal). Other data repositories are unable to provide an API due to legal reasons. For example the GRDC are prohibited to offer an API access point, since they require identified access and explicit (human) acceptance of the Terms of Use and Data Protection REgulations following the WMO Congress (https://www.bafg.de/GRDC/EN/02_srvcs/21_tmsrs/210_prtl/faqs.html). Another consideration that was not measured in this report, is whether databases allow the download of temporally or geographically specific pieces of data or if data needs to be downloaded in pre-described batches of data.

3.9 End-users

End-users are a diverse group, similarly to the data providers, with different levels of expertise and needs. Satellite-EO based end-users include: university students, researchers with different levels of expertise, and water managers. Different repositories have different end-users in mind, which was discussed in Section 2.3. Some are more aimed towards the public, while others are serving the needs of a specific group of the scientific community or the national environmental framework. The number of end-users is not available for most data repositories. For those that were available, there is a very large range, for example LIMNADES had 170 registered users in total, while open repositories such as GEMstat have around 400 per year (Table 9). Open repositories overall have very large numbers of users but for the relevant databases or data packages the numbers are lower. The number of citations largely depends on the acknowledgement requirements for different data, which is stipulated by the

repository and the data providers. Pangaea, Zenodo and Hydroshare give usage details per package.

Table 9. *Estimated number of users for repositories where possible and corresponding number of citations retrieved using Google Scholar in Jan 2023.*

Repository name	Estimated number of users
LIMNADES	~170 registered users in total
GRDC	~700 per month
GEMstat	~400 per year
ISIMIP (lake sector)	~200 total
VESLA	~110 registered users total

4. Future needs and recommendations

The organisation and storage of in-situ data are important influencing factors in the compatibility of in-situ data with satellite-EO data. In this section, the focus will be to 1) consider the best practises for organising and storing in-situ data for different applications with satellite-EO data, 2) identify the barriers in providing this, and 3) offer some future scenarios for improving the storage of in-situ data for uptake in satellite-EO products.

4.1 Barriers to the uptake/use of in-situ data repositories by satellite-EO end-users

The review of existing in-situ data repositories highlighted some substantial challenges and barriers to the uptake of in-situ data by the satellite-EO data user community. Here, some of the key overall challenges are highlighted, but it is important to note that the list of repositories included in this report was not exhaustive, and all the data within the repositories were not inspected.

The key issues were as follows;

- Inland and coastal in-situ data are scattered across many different repositories, in many different formats and with different levels of accessibility. A lack of standardised datasets / many inconsistent datasets from different sources. A lack of transboundary datasets. This is a barrier for new or potential users looking for specific variables or spatio-temporal data. This is also a barrier for bigger scale attempts to gather and standardise relevant data to facilitate the use within the satellite-EO community
- Repositories (and monitoring schemes or sampling campaigns) are often not designed or focused on inland and coastal communities (e.g. limnologists, oceanographers), nor for EO communities, which is hence reflected by:
 - A lack of radiometric data
 - A lack of data from both inland and coastal waters
 - A lack of in-situ data that matches up with satellite overpasses
 - A lack of data already formatted to be matched up with EO data

- Although previous deliverables have reported the need for greater water quality data, in the analysis and the repositories presented in this study, we found similar representation compared to water quantity.
- Repositories, particularly project-based repositories tend to be poorly maintained - often 'frozen' or 'abandoned' after the project end-date
- Repositories are often difficult to be accessed by new users (e.g. require a login before clarity on what datasets are available)
- Lack of machine-readability prohibits automated data gathering which would be necessary for many applications

Coupling satellite-EO data with in-situ data can be done with various applications and can have different barriers (Table 10). Many of these barriers are related to the collection of data (see D4.2 for greater detail), the organisation of data within a repository or across many repositories.

Table 10. Some of the challenges to the use of in-situ data repositories for applications that couple satellite-EO and in-situ inland/coastal data. This is not an exhaustive list of applications or needs.

	Needs for satellite-EO applications
Data availability and collection practises	<p>Need for more water-leaving reflectance data or other radiometric quantities that match-up with satellite overpasses for cal/val.</p> <p>Need for more lake water reflectance, Inherent Optical Properties and water constituents data for algorithm development and calibration.</p> <p>Secured-buoy data for precision georeferencing (e.g. AERONET-OC buoys)</p> <p>Need for more representation of small lakes and rivers (CCVS, 2022)</p>
Distribution of data across repositories	<p>Need for gathering/generating large harmonised datasets to be representative of spatio-temporal resolution of satellite data and the variability of inland/coastal water bodies.</p> <p>Relevant for almost all satellite applications especially for training AI models and machine learning, data fusion and downscaling and reconstruction of missing data (e.g. deadlines, gaps, cloud cover).</p>
Formatting of data	<p>Data needs to be manually formatted by matching up in-situ data with satellite overpasses for validation & determining the uncertainty of the satellite data.</p> <p>Data needs to be manually formatted for consistency across sources, and enough information to determine the uncertainty in the in-situ data itself.</p>
Access of data	<p>Data needs to be uploaded in a timely fashion to be useful for any real-time applications or predictive modelling.</p> <p>Automated machine-readable data access is needed for inclusion of data into operational early warning applications etc.</p>

4.2 Challenges faced by in-situ data providers, gatherers, and database managers

In-situ database providers face various challenges in ensuring these data are effectively used. We identify some of the key barriers. These include;

- **Funding barriers;** the most obvious challenge to providing a repository is funding. All aspects of data collection, storage and organisation are influenced by the amount of funding and the resources provided to curate and maintain the data repository. Some key examples of challenges which have funding barriers are:
 - Project funding does not cover the storage of data
 - Project funding does not cover the maintenance of database after project end-date
 - Time for data management is not included in the project funding
 - Insufficient funding for the desired harmonisation, quality control etc of data
 - Longevity of funding is not confirmed
- **Complexity/skill barriers:** Many different aspects of in-situ data storage and organisation require specific skills and experience which can be a barrier. Examples of challenges that have complexity barriers are below:
 - Building a data repository (especially in academic context)
 - Formatting spectral data to be matched-up with satellite data
 - Metadata for spectral/radiometric data can be complicated and requires experienced persons (see Table 3; metadata requirements from LIMNADES)
 - Data ownership / hybrid requires automated or manual request and permission process
 - Data ownership requires legal understanding and many times it depends on laws set by different countries
 - Effective automated quality check or data processing
- **Time/effort barriers:** Even where the funding is available, some of the requirements are time consuming and arduous. These include:
 - Harmonising and standardising data from different sources

- Need for manual quality check and assurance prior to publishing data
- Formatting data, especially matched-up data can be highly time consuming (Pavlehan et al., 2021).
- **Social/organisational barriers** - data repositories may not be optimised by data providers or users for various reasons including:
 - Reluctance by potential users to use the repository even if the criteria for uptake are met
 - Lack of incentive for data providers to submit data or to meet the necessary quality and metadata requirements
 - Lack of attribution for data gatherers to sustain repositories

4.4 Recommendations

Alignment between data collection, data gatherers and end-users

As noted in other deliverables (e.g. D4.2, in-situ workshop), there is a strong need for greater alignment between data producers, providers, gatherers, managers, funders and end-users. It was also apparent from this review, that inland and coastal data users, and the satellite-EO community, are not a priority to many in-situ data producers or repository curators. When evaluating, planning and executing any future actions to improve the uptake of in-situ data by the satellite-EO community, it will be necessary to get input from all stakeholders. For example, data producers and end-users need to communicate to determine how data producers can be incentivised to produce high-quality data and how end-users can get relevant and sufficient data for their applications, with particular focus on enhancing the match-up with satellite overpasses (Carvalho et al., 2021). Aligning may also require agencies and service providers of satellite data products to become more involved in the collection and long-term monitoring of necessary in-situ measurements (Loew et al., 2017). Another aspect may include the standardisation of practises for in-situ observation networks (D4.2), or alternative observational data (D4.4). Notably, however, standardisation will require a 'to-and-fro' process, since both data producers and data users need to have their needs met to make a sustainable alliance. In addition, it is worth noting that the goal is not always to have a perfectly uniform data collection

regime, particularly in areas where the methodologies are still evolving. As noted by Pahlevan et al. (2021) when collecting radiometric in-situ data to match with satellite data for the ACIX-Aqua, “creating a large pool of data using a combination of various methods likely minimizes any systematic errors in our performance assessments”.

Centralised coordination

There is also a real need to capture and review the scope and efforts of different repositories and initiatives across the EU, and globally. Following this report, a systematic review is suggested to map the global availability of relevant in-situ data for use with satellite-Eo data and identify the gaps for different scientific communities. One of the criticisms of scientific data, is that repositories or databases are often developed for a short-term project or in response to the specific needs of a group of scientists, and may not be useful, accessible or compatible with the needs of the wider scientific community. Hence, careful analysis is necessary to optimise the use of a repository. Analysis or overview could be useful in discerning where needs are being fully met, where re-organisation is needed, whether an existing repository can be expanded or where a complete gap exists. This might include identifying all current repositories, substantial monitoring schemes, and even grasp the amount of less formal data, including that from low-cost sensors or citizen science. A following dissemination activity might be how to maximise the data that are already available. For this we can investigate projects such as the MONOCLE project, where data were harmonised from various sources including low-cost sensors or citizen science sources. Maximising the use of existing data may also involve increasing the profile of existing data and accessibility of data, while also providing capacity building activities to prohibit barriers to uptake.

Promoting open-access data

Open-access oriented science could also save a lot of problems, but there is a need to compensate or incentivise data producers. When data are open-access it removes the need for repositories to manage the release of the data. It also allows data to be uploaded efficiently so it can be used rapidly after collection, which is essential for applications such as near real-time monitoring or early warning systems (e.g. cyanobacteria alert).

Greater focus on data management

Data management in general may be often overlooked within the planning of academic projects, by project-funding agents and also at the institutional level. If thorough data management plans are required as part of project proposals, it may help to ensure that data are made accessible before the end of a project and time/resource costs of doing so can be included in the funding of the project. Funding agents may consider including greater scrutinisation of the data management of projects, as part of the funding criteria, including what will happen to the repository or database after the project. At the institutional level there could be greater investment in permanent data repository curators and managers, who have the expertise and time to work on the maintenance and consistency of datasets and improve the usability of data that institutions produce. A focus on data management is likely to increase the trust of potential users, interpretability and usability of in-situ data in general.

Greater focus on new or potential users

There are very large barriers faced by new or potential users, whether this be due to 1) insufficient discovery metadata, 2) barriers to accessing the data, 3) lack of educational/instructional guide on how to use the data, 4) lack of metadata and interpretability, 5) lack of trust in the data. Although repositories mostly meet FAIR requirements (see D4.5), there is a substantial way to go before the data are fully accessible to a member of the general public, an undergraduate student or a water manager, and are fully maximised in its possible use.

To achieve this, data management standards may also be imposed to ensure that new data are FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) and also TRUSTworthy (Transparency, Responsibility, User Focus, Sustainability, Technology) (Lin et al., 2020). Repository registrars like “Core Trust Seal” and “Re3” can help ensure the standards of repositories, but more specific requirements for the satellite-EO community may be used in addition. Greater harmonisation in the practises of different repositories (e.g. of data formatting, metadata and quality checks), may allow users to gather data from different

locations with greater ease, thus addressing a key challenge currently faced by satellite-EO users.

4.4 Future possibilities for storing in-situ data

There are various future options for storing in-situ data for the purpose of coupling with satellite-EO data. Some of these possible options are considered here.

4.4.1 Metadata repositories for in-situ data

One option is a metadata repository that facilitates the discovery of in-situ data for the use with satellite-EO data. Currently there is no designated metadata repository that offers a central access point for different inland and coastal in-situ data repositories. GEOSS and NETLAKE, however, both include in-situ data that could be used with satellite-EO data. The main benefit of metadata repositories is likely to be the discovery of data, connecting users (e.g., Copernicus) to in situ data providers. A metadata repository could also provide an overview of data options, for example, with a map-based browser to guide users to relevant data providers. This may improve clarity on where the data gaps are and also improve communication between data providers and satellite-EO based end-users. A metadata repository removes the risk of copying data and may have lower curation and maintenance costs than a data hosting repository, although if it is to be useful it would need to be sustainably funded. Notably, however, a metadata repository does not necessarily meet many of the requirements of many of the satellite-EO data applications, but may be a good feasible option, in the right direction. Another option would be to have a Re3 type central body which coordinates all EU-based data repositories, which could require certain metadata standards to be met.

4.4.2 Extend an existing database

Data repositories that are already storing in-situ data for inland and coastal waters could be extended, with sufficient funding and resources, to further meet the needs of the satellite-EO community. For example, SeaBASS and LIMNADES are both vital in providing match-up data between in-situ reference data and satellite overpasses. SeaBASS for example, could be expanded to include more

inland water data. LIMNADES could also be refunded, upgraded, and expanded to include more match-up data or the accessibility and findability could be enhanced to ensure the data are more widely used. Other repositories, such as PANGAEA, may also already have the framework, capacity and flexibility to house the existing or new data.

4.4.3 A built-for-purpose repository

A built-for-purpose data repository could be designed with the intention and purpose of storing and organising data for different applications with satellite-EO data. A model for this might be adopted from existing managed open data repositories included in this report (e.g. GEMsWater), where data are consolidated from many sources and can be well presented for new end-users. A designated in-situ data repository would need to standardise and reformat data from various sources, into a centralised data system. Lessons on how to do this efficiently might also be learnt from the MONOCLE repository and also the SWatCH and ACIX-Aqua projects. There are many challenges in building a specific repository, and preparation would require considering and recruiting the advice of all stakeholders (i.e. data providers, different end-users), to ensure the repository is well-received and used. Moreover, a substantial amount of effort and funding would be required and hence the need for the repository would need to be confirmed. This may include determination of the exact scope (.e.g, inland and coastal data only, for validation or all coupling with in-situ data). Flexibility would also be advised, considering how rapidly the methods of the satellite-EO community evolve. Similarly, data repository curation and commonly accepted data formats also change over time and would require specialist knowledge to ensure longevity.

Funding and organisation structure could take various forms. One example is that storage space is made available to EU-based national or long-term monitoring schemes on the EOS cloud, alleviating costs for data storage by institutions. In return, collection protocol may be encouraged, promoting harmonisation across data producers and the uptake of practices relevant for satellite-EO applications. Alternatively, the liaison, management and

harmonisation of data could be carried out by a data harmonising agent, which could potentially be a new space for a business innovation.

5. Conclusion

The organisation and storage of in-situ data are important in the coupling of in-situ and satellite-EO data. A number of existing inland and coastal data repositories were reviewed in this report. The review highlighted various unmet needs from the satellite-EO community as well as from data curators and managers responsible for gathering, organising and storing data. This report can be used as a starting place for future efforts to align the different stakeholders (e.g. data producers, gatherers and end-users) to improve the uptake of in-situ data in satellite-EO based applications.

References

Carvalho, L., Ruescas, A., Stelzer, K., Brockmann, C., Taylor, P., Dobel, A., Nash, G. and Fry, M., 2021. Lake water quality in-situ data requirements and availability. Copenhagen, European Environment Agency, 70pp. (Unpublished).

CCVS, 2022, D2.6 - Cal/Val Data Distribution. Available at: <https://www.ccvv.eu/deliverables> (Accessed: Jan 2023).

GEMs/Water, 2019, GEMS water strategy 2020-2024, Available at: https://communities.unep.org/download/attachments/27591258/GEMS%20Water%20Strategy_2020-2024.pdf?version=1&modificationDate=1611917955221&api=v2 (Accessed: Jan 2023).

Golub, M., Thiery, W., Marcé, R., Pierson, D., Vanderkelen, I., Mercado-Bettin, D., Woolway, R.I., Grant, L., Jennings, E., Kraemer, B.M. and Schewe, J., 2022. A framework for ensemble modelling of climate change impacts on lakes worldwide: the ISIMIP Lake Sector. *Geoscientific Model Development*, 15(11), pp.4597-4623.

Lehner, B., Messenger, M.L., Korver, M.C., Linke, S. (2022). Global hydro-environmental lake characteristics at high spatial resolution. *Scientific Data* 9: 351. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-022-01425-z>

Lin, D., Crabtree, J., Dillo, I., Downs, R.R., Edmunds, R., Giaretta, D., De Giusti, M., L'Hours, H., Hugo, W., Jenkyns, R. and Khodiyar, V., 2020. The TRUST Principles for digital repositories. *Scientific Data*, 7(1), pp.1-5.

Linke, S., Lehner, B., Ouellet Dallaire, C., Ariwi, J., Grill, G., Anand, M., Beames, P., Burchard-Levine, V., Maxwell, S., Moidu, H., Tan, F., Thieme, M. (2019). Global hydro-environmental sub-basin and river reach characteristics at high spatial resolution. *Scientific Data* 6: 283. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-019-0300-6>

Loew, A., Bell, W., Brocca, L., Bulgin, C.E., Burdanowitz, J., Calbet, X., Donner, R.V., Ghent, D., Gruber, A., Kaminski, T. and Kinzel, J., 2017. Validation practices for satellite-based Earth observation data across communities. *Reviews of Geophysics*, 55(3), pp.779-817.

Pahlevan, N., Mangin, A., Balasubramanian, S.V., Smith, B., Alikas, K., Arai, K., Barbosa, C., Bélanger, S., Binding, C., Bresciani, M. and Giardino, C., 2021. ACIX-Aqua: A global assessment of atmospheric correction methods for Landsat-8 and Sentinel-2 over lakes, rivers, and coastal waters. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 258, p.112366.

Rimet, F., Anneville, O., Barbet, D., Chardon, C., Crepin, L., Domaizon, I., Dorioz, J.M., Espinat, L., Frossard, V., Guillard, J. and Goulon, C., 2020. The Observatory on LAkes (OLA) database: Sixty years of environmental data accessible to the public. *Journal of Limnology*, 79(2), pp.164-178.

Rotteveel, L., Heubach, F. and Sterling, S.M., 2022. The Surface Water Chemistry (SWatCh) database: A standardized global database of water chemistry to facilitate large-sample hydrological research. *Earth System Science Data*, 14(10), pp.4667-4680.

Spyrakos, E., Hunter, P., Simis, S., Neil, C., Riddick, C., Wang, S., Varley, A., Blake, M., Groom, S., Palenzuela, J.T. and Gonzalez, L.V., 2020, March. Moving towards global satellite based products for monitoring of inland and coastal waters. Regional examples from Europe and South America. In *2020 IEEE Latin American GRSS & ISPRS Remote Sensing Conference (LAGIRS)* (pp. 363-368). IEEE.

Supplementary Material

Table S1. List of *in situ* requirements for all relevant products (water quantity and water quality)

Requirement for existing products	No. Products	Firm	Reasonable	Speculative	Tentative	Unknown	Calibration and validation	Product generation	Supporting exploitation	Desirable	Essential	Optional	Useful	Unknown	Fully	Partially	Unknown	Accuracy	Availability	Coverage	Data policy	Resolution	Timeliness	Update Frequency	Unknown
Land Cover	25	24	1				2	23		1	24				25			18	7						
Meteorological Information	23	23						23			23				23			23							
Sea Surface Temperature	22	15	7				12	10			22				21	1			10	11					1
Pan-European hydrological models	20	20						20			20				20			16	1						3
Physiography	18	18						18			18				15	3		15	3						
Hydrological information	16	16						16			16				16			16							
Built-up Area	14	14						14			14					14		13							1
Digital Elevation Model	14	14						14			14				6	1	7	5	6			3			
Radar Rainfall Information	14	14						14			14				14			14							
Administrative boundaries	12	12						12			12				12			7	3					2	
Historical meteorology	12	8	4					12		1	11				12			12							

Water - ForCE

Land Cover - Inland Water Bodies & Wetland Fraction	10		1	9			10		10				10		10					
Hydrographic network	9		3	6			3	6		9			9		9					
Sea level	9		9				9		9				9		6	3				
Global hydrological modelling	8		8				8		8			8		8						
Hydrological Information Global	8		8				8		8			8		8						
Meteorological forecast global	8		8				8		8			8		8						
Hydrography	6		6				1	5		6			6		5					1
Orthoimagery - Very High Resolution - Up-to-date - Homogenous	6		6				6		6			6		6						
Oxygen	6		6				6		6			6		6						
Subsurface Salinity	6		2	4			2	4		2		4		6						
subsurface temperature	6		2	4			1	3	2	1	5		6		6					
Digital Elevation Model (global)	5		5				5		5			5		5		5				
Industry and Utilities	5		5				5		5			5		5		5				
River Discharge	5		1	4			5		5			1	4		5					
Settlements - Building Block	5		5				5		5			5		5		5				
Transportation network	5		4	1			5		1	4			5		5					
Air Temperature (at surface)	4			4			3	1		4			4		1	2				1
Chlorophyll	4			4			4		4			4		4		1	3			
Hydrography network	4		4				4		4			2	2		2		2			

Water - ForCE

OrthoImagery	3		3				1	2	1		2	3			3				
Settlements - Building Footprint	3			3			3			3			3			3			
Settlements - Built-Up Areas	3	2	1				2	1	1	2			3			3			
Topographic maps	3			3			3			3			3		1	2			
Toponyms	3	3					3			3			3			3			
Vegetation Ground Measurements	3	1	2				3			2	1		3		3				
Volcanic soils, 100+ m resolution	3	3					3			3			3		3				
Air Pressure (at surface)	2				2			2	2				2						2
Horizontal wind vector (at surface)	2	1	1				2		1	1			2						2
Inorganic carbon (DIC, TA, pCO2, pH)	2			1	1		2			1		1	2		2				
Land Cover - Forest	2	2					2			2			2						2
Land Cover / Land Use, 100+ m resolution	2	2					2			2					2				2
Land Use	2		2			2					2		2						2
Meteorological Geographical Features	2			2			2			2			2						2
Sea Ice cover	2		2				2				2		2						2
Snow Depth Ground Measurements	2		2				2			2			1	1		1	1		
Soil map	2	2					2			2			2		1	1			

Water - ForCE

Toponyms (Place Names)	2	2					2		2			2						2
10-days Snow Anomaly	1	1					1		1			1						1
Atmospheric parameters	1			1			1	1				1						1
Atmospheric temperature (upper air)	1		1				1	1				1						1
Combined Drought Indicator	1		1				1		1			1						1
Flood Hazard Map	1	1					1		1			1						1
Glacier coverage	1	1					1		1			1						1
Global in situ Soil Moisture Database	1	1					1		1			1						1
Gridded global precipitation (monthly)	1	1					1		1			1						1
Gridded Monthly Land-Surface Precipitation	1	1					1		1			1						1
Gridded precipitations (daily)	1	1					1		1			1						1
Ground Control Points (GCPs) - 2D	1	1					1		1			1						1
Ground Control Points (GCPs) - 3D	1			1			1		1			1						1
Historical meteorology global	1		1			1		1				1						1
Horizontal wind vector (upper air)	1	1					1		1			1						1
Hydrography infrastructure	1		1				1		1			1						1
Hydrological modelling	1	1					1		1			1						1

Surface synoptic observations for reporting weather observations	1	1					1		1				1					1	
Transportation and railway network	1	1					1		1				1			1			
Vegetation maps	1	1					1		1				1		1				
Vessels position	1				1			1	1				1						
Wind and Waves parameters	1	1					1		1				1					1	

Table S2. Count of Products which are linked to different datasets, organised by requirement type

Type of database	Count of Products linked to data
Combined Drought Indicator	1
Combined Drought Indicator	1
Flood threshold exceedances	6
GloFAS 30-day - hydrological modelling forecast	3
GloFAS seasonal discharge thresholds	3

Water - ForCE

Global hydrological modelling	56
ECMWF operational forecast (Global)	8
ENS	8
ERA5	8
Global Land Cover 2010	8
Harmonized World Soil Database	8
HydroSHEDS	8
SEAS5	8
Global <i>in situ</i> Soil Moisture Database	1
International Soil Moisture Network	1
Hydrographic network	305
HYDROLARE	29
INSPIRE Annex I: Hydrography	29
Natural Earth Dataset	29
Near real-time Global Flood Monitoring (GFM)	29

OpenStreetMap	29
River and Catchment Database (CCM)	29
Shuttle Radar Topography Mission Water Body Dataset (SWBD)	29
Vector Map1 (VMap1)	29
Wikimapia	29
World Countries Open Data: Hydrography	29
(blank)	15
Hydrography	40
EU-HYDRO	10
European Catchments and Rivers Network System (ECRINS)	8
EuroRegionalMap	2
OpenStreetMap	6
Shuttle Radar Topography Mission Digital Elevation Model (SRTM DEM) - 30 m	6
Water Information System in Europe (WISE) Water Framework Directive database	8

Hydrography infrastructure	3
European Catchments and Rivers Network System (ECRINS)	1
Global Reservoir and Dam (GRanD) database	1
Managing Aquatic ecosystems and water Resources under multiple Stress spatial database (MARSgeoDB)	1
Hydrography network	14
Hydrography Network	8
INSPIRE Annex I: Hydrography	6
Hydrological information	48
COSMO-LEPS operational forecast	16
LISFLOOD operational forecast	16
River Discharge	16
Hydrological Information Global	16
ERA5T	8
(blank)	8
Hydrological modelling	11

Water - ForCE

COSMO-EU	1
ERA-Interim	1
Flood reporting points	1
Real-time Hydrographs	1
(blank)	7
Lake extent polygons	3
PML lake polygons dataset	3
Optical water types	3
Optical water types	3
Pan-European hydrological models	180
ECMWF operational forecast (Global)	20
ERICHA flash flood indicator	20
Flood reporting points	20
INSPIRE Annex I: Hydrography	20
Land Surface Temperature	20

Water - ForCE

LISFLOOD operational forecast	4
Real-time Hydrographs	20
River Discharge	4
SYNOP based latest 24 hour observed precipitation	20
(blank)	32
Relative soil moisture	1
(blank)	1
River Discharge	2
Hydrological Data Collection Centre	1
LISFLOOD operational forecast	1
Seasonal Outlook	1
(blank)	1
Soil Moisture Anomaly	1
(blank)	1
Total Water Storage (TWS)	1

Water - ForCE

Total Water Storage	1
Water Colour and Temperature Ground Measurements	28
All Corners of the Earth (EUSTACE) project	4
ATSR Reprocessing for Climate (ARC)	4
Globalakes	4
Lake salinity	4
LIMNADES	4
STORET database	4
Water Quality Portal	4